

Effect of various pre-treatments for breaking the dormancy of *Desmodium gangeticum* DC.

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Abstract

In the present investigation, seeds of *Desmodium gangeticum* were subjected to various treatments to achieve early germination by breaking dormancy.

A cursory look at the table 1 indicates that only 19% of *D. gangeticum* seeds could germinate under controlled conditions. Whereas, a germination percentage of 91 was achieved in the stratified seeds followed by 71% under the influence of IAA and 57% under brassinolide treatment. In this way, stratification is the best method for breaking the seed dormancy of *D. gangeticum*.

The seeds of some plants easily germinate after sowing in nature but the seeds of a number of plants do not germinate easily and exhibit dormancy for varying period of time. The dormancy may be due to internal factors or may be due to external factors. Certain plants may immediately germinate after the harvest, it can be best exemplified by the seeds of *Pisum sativum*, which sometimes germinate in the fruit itself which is still on the plant, a phenomenon known as vivipary. However, sometimes the dormancy period is very prolonged and can take months together for germination. This is true for the seeds of *Malus domestica* which has a hard seed coat and *Entada gigas* which has a very thick seed coat and do not germinate easily.

Desmodium gangeticum is a herbaceous plant of the family Fabaceae and grows wild often under the shade of trees. It

produces numerous lomentum fruits. The plant is used medicinally by the practioners of indigenous system of medicine. It is useful in neuro-muscular disorders. It has antifungal and antibacterial activity. It is also useful in typhoid, tuberculosis, cough, seminal weakness and diarrhoea. The plant is known as *Shaalaparni* or *Sarivan*.

The seeds of this medicinally important plant show dormancy because only 19% germination was found till 17th day of sowing in untreated seeds. Therefore, it was thought imperative to undertake this investigation to find out the substance that can break the dormancy of this plant. The seeds were subjected to various treatments which are mentioned in table 1.

According to Berlyn (1972), germination is a sequential series of morphogenetic events

that result in the transformation of an embryo into a seedling. The seeds of every plant have the capability to germinate but their germination is affected due to some factors, such as seed coat, hard seed coat, rudiment embryo, over-ripening, presence of plant growth inhibitors, due to absence of water, oxygen and due to unfavourable conditions. Dormancy of seeds is due to external factors or due to internal factors. When it is caused due to internal factors, it is called as true dormancy or innate dormancy or primary dormancy. And when it is caused due to external factors, it is called as imposed dormancy or quiescent dormancy or secondary dormancy. Both of these primary and secondary dormancy influences are mutually dependent and can not be singled out. True dormant seeds do not germinate even if they are provided with suitable environmental factors. Secondary dormant seeds may germinate immediately after shed off. After some storage, they fail to germinate and thus exhibit secondary dormancy. Some seeds such as *Brassica alba*, *Ambrosia tripolia* and *Xanthium pennsylvanicum* exhibit secondary dormancy. Secondary dormancy is opposite to after ripening. Presence of high carbondioxide concentration, absence of light and very high or low temperature induce the secondary dormancy.

A number of techniques are available for breaking the dormancy of seeds, such as; scarification, exposure to light, alternating high & low temperatures, stratification, impaction, pressure, electric current, pretreatment with coumarins, kinetin, GA₃, H₂SO₄, thiourea, KNO₃ and hot water.

Studies on germination and dormancy of seeds have been carried out by various

workers on different types of species. These include; the studies of Shul (1911) on the oxygen minimum and the germination of *Xanthium* seeds. A detailed account of seed dormancy mechanics was given by Crocker (1916). Influence of low temperature in improving germination percentage was found out by Conville, (1920). Similarly, alternating temperatures to break the dormancy was used by Harrington, (1923). Morinaga (1926) has studied the germination of seeds under water.

Davis (1928) used high pressure to achieve higher seed germination. Denny & Stanton, (1928) suggested chemical treatments for breaking the seed dormancy. Joseph, (1929) investigated the germination and vitality of birch seeds. Barton (1930) investigated on coniferous seeds. In 1936, Crocker investigated the effect of visible spectrum upon the germination of seeds and fruits. In 1938, Crocker also gave an account of life-span of seeds.

Chouard⁵ has investigated vernalization and its relation to dormancy. Experimental induction of dormancy in *Betula pubescens* was investigated by Eagles & Wareing⁹. Evanari,¹¹ has studied the physiology of seed dormancy, after ripening and germination. Ribosome and enzyme changes during maturation and germination of the castor bean seeds was investigated by Marre,¹⁶. Effects of light, temperature and their interaction on the germination of seeds was investigated by Toole²⁷.

Hayes & Klein,¹³ investigated special quality influence of light during development of *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants in regulating

seed germination. Bewley and Black,² studied the physiology and biochemistry of seeds. Isoenzymes of sugar phosphate metabolism in endosperm of germinating castor beans were studied by Nishimura,²¹. Seed germination and dormancy have been studied by Bewley,³. Improvement of seed germination in *Asparagus racemosus* has been reported by Gupta, *et al.*,¹².

Effect of pre-sowing treatment on seed germination of *Babchi* (*Psoralea corylifolia*) and Senna (*Cassia angustifolia*) in nursery has been reported by Koppad and Umarbhadsha¹⁵. Seed germination behaviour of *Asparagus racemosus* (*Shatavari*) under *in-vivo* and *in-vitro* conditions has been investigated by Raghav and Kasera²². Siva *et al.*,²⁵ have studied the enhanced seed germination of *Psoralea corylifolia* L. by heat treatment. Musara, *et al.*,¹⁹ have investigated the evaluation of different seed dormancy breaking techniques on Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) seed germination. Asha and Illa,¹ have studied the effect of seed direction and growth media on *in vitro* seed germination and seedling establishment of *Pterocarpus marsupium*.

Cantoro, *et al.*,⁴ have reported seed dormancy QTL identification across a *Sorghum bicolor* segregating population. Dave, *et al.*,⁶ have investigated the regulation of *Arabidopsis thaliana* seed dormancy and germination by 12-oxo-phytodienoic acid. *Entada phaseoloids* seed dormancy and germination: implications for conservation and restoration has been reported by Deepa and Shinde⁷. The effect of the use of temperature

on the breakage of dormancy and the subsequent performance of rice (*Oryza* spp.) has been investigated by Doku, *et al.*,⁸. Transcriptome analysis of seed dormancy after rinsing and chilling in ornamental peaches (*Prunus persica*) has been investigated by Kanjana, *et al.*,¹⁴.

Effect of different pretreatments and seed coat on dormancy and germination of seeds of *Senna obtusifolia* has been studied by Mensah and Ekeke¹⁷. Mishra¹⁸ has investigated the effect of temperature and light on the seed germination of *Sida cordifolia*. Redwood, *et al.*,²³ have reported seed longevity and dormancy state in a disturbance-dependent forest herb, *Ageratina*. Germination pretreatments to break hard-seed dormancy in *Astragalus cicer* L. has been studied by Statwick²⁶.

Effect of various dormancy breaking treatments on seed germination, seedling growth and seed vigour of medicinal plants has been investigated by Warghat, *et al.*,²⁸. Zohra, *et al.*,²⁹ have reported the effect of salicylic acid on germination of *Ocimum gratissimum* seeds induced into dormancy by chlormequat. The release of dormancy, a wake-up call for seeds to germinate has reported by Nee, *et al.*,²⁰.

Healthy seeds of *Desmodium gangeticum* were collected from the seed market (Bhopal). The seeds were washed with running tap water three to four times and once surface sterilized with 0.1% H₂CL₂ solution for 5 minutes to remove the surface adhering microbes. After surface sterilization, the seeds were again washed with double distilled water. Uniform sized seeds were then transferred to

Table-1. showing the effect of various treatments on the germination percentage of *D. gangeticum*.

D A S → Treatment	3days	5days	7days	9days	11days	13days	15days	17Days
Control	4	8	8	12	15	19	19	19
Hot water	2	6	7	7	12	16	17	17
Scarification	8	12	15	15	21	27	27	27
Stratification	21	32	49	67	80	91	91	91
Alt. high & low temp.	7	11	17	23	25	31	32	33
KNO ₃	6	10	16	19	23	27	27	27
Thiourea	7	9	9	17	20	24	26	26
Kinetin	9	13	15	18	24	27	27	28
GA ₃	8	12	17	20	23	29	31	31
H ₂ SO ₄	9	13	17	23	29	35	35	35
Presoaking	12	17	23	27	33	39	39	40
Coumarin	0	4	9	13	21	23	27	27
Electric current	8	10	10	13	19	26	28	28
Brassinolide	8	18	24	31	42	57	57	57
Mechanical injury	9	14	18	24	30	30	30	30
IAA	15	28	46	52	60	68	70	71

sterilized Petri Plates provided with filter paper pads.

Three replicates of treated and control seeds were kept for germination studies. The filter paper pads were moistened as and when needed. The emergence of radical was taken as germination.

The germination started on the 3rd day from the date of sowing, both in the treated and untreated seeds except coumarin. It was 4, 2, 8, 21, 7, 6, 7, 9, 8, 9, 12, 8, 9, 0, 8 and 15 percent germination respectively in the seeds kept as control, those treated with hot water, scarification, stratification, alternating high and low temperature, KNO₃, thiourea, kinetin, GA₃,

H₂SO₄, pre-soaking, electric current, mechanical injury, coumarin, brassinolide and IAA. The germination percentage was found increased on 9th day under all the treatments as well as under control. It was 12, 7, 15, 67, 23, 19, 17, 18, 20, 23, 28, 13, 24, 13, 31 and 52 percent respectively in the seeds kept as control and those treated with hot water and subjected to scarification, stratification, alternating high and low temperature, KNO₃, thiourea, kinetin, GA₃, H₂SO₄, pre-soaking, electric current, mechanical injury, coumarin, brassinolide and IAA treatments. On 17th day, the germination percentage was 19, 17, 27, 91, 32, 27, 26, 28, 31, 35, 40, 28, 30, 27, 57 and 71 in the seeds kept as control, those treated with

hot water and subjected to scarification, stratification, alternating high and low temperature, KNO₃, thiourea, kinetin, GA₃, H₂SO₄, pre-soaking, electric current, mechanical injury, coumarin, brassinolide and IAA treatments. As stated above, 91% germination of *D. gangeticum* seeds was recorded in the stratified seeds, other treatments could not improve germination percentage but the seeds treated with IAA exhibited 71% germination (table 1).

D. gangeticum is a medicinal plant and commonly used in Ayurvedic system of medicine. Seeds of this plant are highly dormant, as is evident from table 1, a cursory look at the table 1 indicates that only 19% of *D. gangeticum* seeds could germinate under controlled conditions. Whereas, a germination percentage of 91 was achieved in the stratified seeds followed by 71% under the influence of IAA and 57% under brassinolide treatment. In this way, stratification is the best method for breaking the seed dormancy of *D. gangeticum* which is supported by Etemadi *et al.*,¹⁴ and Razavi and Hajjiboland (2009).

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